

Towards the Institutionalisation of Gender Mainstreaming in Nigeria's National Assembly

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Abstract

The Nigerian political space is characterised by a pervasive inequality between the male and female gender. With reference to the National Assembly (the federal parliament), there is an unmistakable lacuna in gender composition to the detriment of women, and this is in spite of relevant policy initiatives for gender balancing. This article is focussed on identifying the constraints on gender mainstreaming and how the agents of socialisation can be reformed to induce a positive reaction to women representation and participation in Nigeria's political space. The research deploys the qualitative methodology, and sought data from secondary sources. By using the explication of gender classification as the framework of analysis, the research connects the society's gender role designation as the basis for the inadequate opportunities for representation and participation in politics. Finally, recommendations are presented for reworking the roles and responsibilities of critical agents of socialisation in the realisation of the objectives of gender mainstreaming in the National Assembly and other political institutions.

Keywords: Gender; Nigeria; SDGs; MDGs; Beijing Conference

Introduction

The discourse on gender has its intellectual roots in civil society organisations' escalation of feminism as an ideological position that stands against the challenges of inequality between the two human sexes (Easton, 2012; Mackay, 2014). The feminist ideology provided the platform for agitations against the unfair, unjust and discriminatory representation of the female gender, particularly, in the public sphere. This ideological position, represented by the

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three waves of feminism, impacted both policy and theoretical directions for more than three decades. It was indeed, the culmination of efforts of the generations of feminist thinkers that triggered the global search for equality in an unequal world system.

The world system is characterised by inequalities between the male and female person. Indeed, gender inequalities pervade most human endeavours, and thus exist in societies across the world. Accordingly, societies create gender roles for efficient and effective management of tasks and responsibilities, but also inadvertently create room for gender inequality. Perhaps by nature, it is impossible to coexist without allotting gender-specific roles to each of the two sexes, yet, this act breeds inequalities in the juxtaposition of benefits/opportunities and roles/responsibilities. The mixes about benefits/opportunities and roles/responsibilities are more contentious in the public space. They speak directly to the issues of representation and participation in politics. The debates generated by the development influenced the feminist ideological position; which, broadly defined, is embedded in the notion that societies surreptitiously use the differences in the biological make-up of man and woman, to limit the opportunity of women participation and representation in the public space. In response to the nature-induced constraints therefore, the woman deserves some conscious considerations in the course of representation and participation in the public space. It is the consciously designed strategies and mechanisms for female participation and representation that will bridge the gaps of inequality that must have been created by nature.

In the efforts to bridge the gaps, global stakeholders, arguably through the agitations of the three waves of feminism (Snyder, 2008) have been made to continually craft the methods and strategies for the maximum form of inclusion possible for the womenfolk in the public space. For this purpose, there have been numerous treaties and protocols ratified at the international arena to fight inequality and particularly, the exclusion of women in the public space. For instance, one of the most powerful instruments of the United Nations is the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), where it is made clear that all humans are equal, irrespective of race, gender, colour, creed, language and nationality. And furthermore, they all should be given equal opportunities to attain their potentials. This cogent decision is domesticated in the enabling laws of every member-state of the United Nations.

In more recent times, the gender inequality discourse has arguably received the most attention in the public space among the various human inequalities that exist. The distinctive physiological make-up between male and female have caused various dimensions of inequalities between both sexes, hence, causing the attention of stakeholders to renewed efforts towards the creation of just, fair, and equitable societies across the world. A most potent response to the issues is the UN's recognition of gender mainstreaming as an avenue to achieving gender equality (UN, 2002: 1). This is a method by which conscious efforts are made to ensure both genders, in spite of society-imposed limitations on women in particular, are granted equitable and fair opportunities for representation and participation in the public arena.

Across the world, nations continue to forge forward in the quest for equitable systems in the public arena. Even in Africa where there is some level of acknowledged traditional socio-cultural bias against women, Rwanda has been known to make giant strides in respect of gender mainstreaming through women representation and participation in the public space (Wallace, Haerpfer and Abbot, 2009: 112). Though, a lot of African countries are lagging behind in this endeavour. This research is specifically focussed on the Nigerian situation, by examining Nigeria's progress in respect of gender mainstreaming in political office-participation and representation. The searchlight is on Nigeria's National Assembly (federal parliament); it is a two-chamber parliament (the Senate and the House of Representatives) that is composed of elected representatives of people from all of Nigeria's constituent units. The research dissects the extent to which the Nigerian state has implemented the gender mainstreaming protocol as reflected in the ratio of male and female representatives of the two members of the National Parliament since the commencement of the Fourth Republic in 1999.

The research is organised around the understanding of the multi-dimensional nature of gender classification. This is followed by the explication of the challenges restricting the implementation of the gender mainstreaming protocol in Nigeria, despite the demonstration of willingness to actualise the dream. The research commences with the introduction, followed by an articulation of the philosophy, and the reasons for gender mainstreaming. Furthermore, there will be a thorough examination of the global response to gender mainstreaming, particularly the examination of the relevant sections of the Fourth World Conference on Women (Beijing Conference), the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs),

and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Subsequently, we shall examine the extent to which Nigeria has incorporated the dictates of the various goals in the organisation and management of the political space. In this respect, we shall provide an explanation of the constitutional provision for the composition of the National Assembly, and analyse how the reality is either a negation or support of the provisions. Finally, we provide some recommendations that will enhance the prospects of gender mainstreaming in the National Assembly, and by extension, the political arena in general.

Gender Classification

The concept of gender is complex and subjective. The complex nature results from its definitional fluidity, by which it lends itself to variations because of its relational character. In effect, it is the context that determines how the concept of gender may be understood. Also, the subjective nature of the concept is a derivative of its normative character; being an idea that finds expression within human societies. The implication therefore is that each society places its own value and nuances on the concept of gender. Extant literature, such as, Chaffee et al. (2020); Obioma et al. (2022); Katuk (2023) and Bandura (1999); WHO (2022); UN (2022) and Heidari et al. (2016) provide some illumination on how the concept of gender can be understood. The understanding is however reinforced by the acceptance of gender's multi-dimensional character, which includes its relevance to socio-cultural debates and contentions, explanation about physiological structure, the nature of human biology/anatomy, and discourses about psycho-social well-being. In effect, gender issues transcend the binary perspectives about sex hormones and their complexities (Chaffee et al., 2020 & Katuk, 2023).

Unarguably, gender is closely associated with sex or hormonal classifications, but the two concepts stand distinctly apart when critically analysed. While sex classification is a biological construct that is embedded in genealogy and reproductive anatomy, gender classification encapsulates the totality of socially constructed inclinations with impacts beyond biological or physiological viewpoints (Bandura, 1999; Heidari et al., 2016 & Katuk, 2023). Accordingly, the United Nations (2022) view gender as a product of socially-constructed differences in opportunities and attributes that are based on considerations of being either a male or female, and the social relationship and interaction between men and women. Suffice it therefore to opine that gender is more meaningful as an idea with implications on socio-cultural relations, than a biological construct. From the socio-cultural

perspective, the concept of gender is known to be dynamic, for it easily adapts to constant changes in social roles and abilities. Thus, it is the society that is best placed to determine the character of gender construct since each society presents its own jaundiced role expectations of man/woman and girl/boy. These gender roles are deepened by the ever dynamic process of socialisation.

In a similar vein, gender is perceived as a form of socially constructed identities, images, and perceptions which influence how men and women interact in relations to the distribution of power, resources, and positions, etc. in the society (Heidari, Babor and Curno (2016). By extension, gender issues are focused on normative expectations regarding how men and women should behave and react with respect to access to resources, power, and status in the society. This highlights the centrality of the society in gender classification because of the role it plays in determining the norms and value systems about the perceptions of the roles of men and women in relation to power acquisition and resource accumulation.

In the quest for free, just, and equitable environments, modern societies are redefining the roles and perceptions of men and women in the efforts towards participation and representation in the public space. In this respect, there are series of global efforts towards reworking the narrative about the concept of gender in the public sphere. As Acker (2009) poignantly points out thus:

Gender is based on hierarchical categories which reproduces and reinforces inequalities, discrimination and stereotypes which create intersectionality based on its relationship with ethnicity, socio-economic status, gender identity, geographical location and sexual orientation.

In reaction to the above unflattering tendency towards women, global stakeholders have made several attempts to prevent gender inequalities and imbalances, particularly in the public arena. This is based on the logic that women deserve adequate and commensurate representation and participation in matters affecting their livelihood and well-being.

Gender Mainstreaming as Panacea to Gender Inequality

Gender mainstreaming is a strategy that seeks to institutionalise the ideals of gender equality in the public sphere- public offices, policies, projects and programmes (United Nations,

2022). The goal of gender mainstreaming is to regulate the process of equal access to opportunities and benefits that are open to both the men and women folks. In this regard, gender mainstreaming is focussed on establishing structures and processes that allow for equal access to power, resources, status and position, human rights, and justice systems, by both sexes. Accordingly, the objective is that gender mainstreaming takes cognizance of obstacles to representation and access to opportunities, and therefore infuse mechanisms that provide legal and institutional support for equal access to representation and opportunities.

It seeks to ensure that both men and women contribute and participate equitably in the public sphere, such that they have equal rights, equal voices and capacity to influence conditions that shape their lives. The necessity for gender mainstreaming is triggered by the disproportionate roles, and access to opportunities that women encounter in a male-dominated world. This is exemplified by the statistics presented by UN Women (2019) thus:

23 percent earn less than men; 35 percent of women suffer from sexual-intimate partner or physical violence; women between the age of 23 and 54 years have 63 percent in the labour force participation rate compared to 94 percent men; there are 49 countries without laws against domestic violence; women represent only 24 percent of all parliamentarians as at 2019 and only 11 women serve as Heads of State while 12 serve as Heads of Government.

Gender mainstreaming is the international policy initiative that addresses the ever increasing gender inequality that exists in most societies across the world. In Africa, gender inequality is embedded in the traditional system, and has equally been adapted into the structures and processes of modern governance. Consequently, institutional hindrances that exist in no small measures are erected to prevent the existence of equal playing fields for both men and women in the competition for representation and access to equal opportunities. Indeed, the African ecosystem is becoming increasingly unhealthy for women as they suffer from stereotypes, gender bias and gender inequality in all aspect of the society-family, business, politics and the workplace (Vida, 2020). The limitations imposed by traditional norms and the acquiescence of the institutions of a male-dominated political space ensure that women suffer from unequal access to power, resources, healthcare, and leadership positions. The unjust and unfair systems can only be eradicated through the institutionalisation of gender mainstreaming strategies that are domesticated across African states. Without doubt, gender mainstreaming

remains the most effective strategy needed to address growing gender inequality and ensure empowerment of women, as it integrates gender sensitivity into all policy programmes, structures and functions of all institutions (Caywood & Darmstadt, 2024).

Specifically, gender mainstreaming will ensure that policy making and legislative processes are of greater benefits to all and sundry by addressing the needs of all members of the society, irrespective of differences in sex. Gender mainstreaming as a strategy makes the design, formulation, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of public policies inclusive and effective and ensures that formal regimes and systems that perpetuate gender inequality are removed (UN Women, 2019).

Gender mainstreaming methods are deployed to provide level playing field between both sexes under all circumstances relating to the issues of representation and participation. The process takes cognizance of the number of open opportunities, and allocates specific number of representation/participation slots to the women. In other words, mainstreaming ensures there is a specific ratio of available representation reserved for women. For this purpose, five specific principles are highlighted for taking action, these are; gender-sensitive language, gender-specific data collection and analysis, equal access to and utilisation of services, women and men are equally involved in decision-making, equal treatment is integrated into steering processes.

Global Response to Gender Mainstreaming

Back in 1995, the fourth global response to gender inequality took place at the Beijing Platform for Action as part of the United Nations World Conference on Women in China. Prior to the landmark Beijing Conference, the United Nations had organised similar conferences in Mexico City in 1975, Copenhagen in 1980, and Nairobi in 1990. All of these were gatherings of global stakeholders on matters of women and their development. One key dominant area in all of these gatherings is the subject of women empowerment geared towards equality with men in all facets of human endeavour.

In Beijing 1995, twelve critical areas were identified “as requiring urgent actions to ensure greater opportunities for men, women, girls and boys”. These twelve critical areas are; women and poverty, education and training of women, women and health, violence against women, women and armed conflict, women and the economy, women in power and decision-making, institutional mechanisms, human rights of women, women and media, women and environment, and the girl-child (UN Women, 2019). After thorough deliberations, the world

(representatives of one hundred and eighty nine member-states of the United Nations) unanimously adopted the Beijing Declaration as an agenda for gender equality and women empowerment (UN Women, 2019).

The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) represents another global response to achieving equity in representation and participation. The declaration provided a momentum for the improvement of the rights and empowerment of women. The 2000 Millennium Declaration mandates states to promote gender equality and empowerment of all women as a strategy to bring an end to hunger, diseases, and also stimulate economic growth and development. It is specifically spelt out in Goal 3 of the MDGs thus: “Promote Gender Equality and Empower Women”. As an adjunct, Target 3A states: “Eliminate gender disparity in primary and secondary education, preferably by 2005, and in all levels of education no later than 2015”.

As with the past efforts, the global gathering for initiating the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) was also intended to push the agenda of gender equality a notch higher. The SDGs align women empowerment with the issue of fundamental human rights, for development can only be guaranteed in a world that accommodates the rights of all, irrespective of gender, race, beliefs, or religious affiliations. The emphasis in Goal 5 is: “Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls”. Gender equality is not only a fundamental human right, but a necessary foundation for a peaceful, prosperous and sustainable world. The resolution at the 2015 Sustainable Development Goals mandates states to integrate gender mainstreaming into their development policies such that there will be synergy between sustainable development and commitments towards protection of human rights and empowerment of women in order to achieve gender equality, while at the same time achieve sustainable development at all levels (UN Women, 2019). As signatories to these resolutions, state-members are required to domesticate the contents in their national laws. Beyond domestication, implementation of the ideals is equally paramount.

Domestication of Beijing Declaration, MDGs, and SDGs in Nigeria

Nigeria was part of the 189 countries that signed and adopted the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action in 1995 (Archibong, Bassey and Nwagbara, 2018). This did not only provide institutional legitimacy for the demand for accountability on women’s rights in Nigeria but also led to the emergence of women’s groups and gender equality advocates

around a broad set of shared aspirations. To domesticate the resolutions at the Beijing Declaration, Millennium Development Goals and Sustainable Development Goals, a number of new laws and policies that seek to achieve gender equality were enacted by both the federal and state governments across Nigeria. For instance, there are gender specific policies in the agricultural sector, and also targeted programmes to increase women's participation in the sector. Furthermore, steps have been taken towards the implementation of aspects of UNSCR 1325, which addresses issues such as; inclusion of women in council of traditional rulers and increase in women's political participation (National Bureau of Statistics, 2018).

Other evidence of giant strides by the Nigerian government in the area of integrating the gender equality and women empowerment resolutions into the national and state laws include the passing of the Violence against Persons Prohibition Law in 2015 (FWASD, 2016). In addition, the Nigerian government has ratified nine of the thirteen major global human rights frameworks in existence, which includes; the International Convention on the Elimination of All forms of Racial Discrimination; Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women; the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and International Covenants on Social and Cultural Rights. Instructively, the "Not Too Young to Run" bill that was passed into law in 2018 reduces the minimum age to contest for public office to 25 years, thereby further enhancing the chances of representation and participation for elective positions for young and qualified Nigerian women (Gender Report, 2019).

In furtherance of the Nigerian government's commitment to the realisation of the goals of the BDPFA, MDGs and SDGs there has been a strong focus on social investment programmes that are geared towards the acceleration of economic growth and women empowerment. From 2016 to 2022, the SIP has enjoyed the benefit of being ranked among recipients of the top five budgetary allocations. The SIP budget is divided into four other programmes such as the National Home Grown Feeding Programmes; N-Power; The Government Enterprise and Empowerment Programme (GEEP), and National Cash Transfer Programme. The budgetary provision for these programmes has remained consistent with N150 billion per budgetary year and with a slight increase in 2016 of N50 billion. SIP budgetary allocation was 11 % in 2016, 7.4% in 2017, 5.6% in 2018 and 7.4% in 2019 (Gender Report, 2019). This is a demonstration of government's commitment to the domestication of international resolutions freely entered into, and by extension, the willingness to execute programmes attached to the resolutions.

However, despite the efforts of the Nigerian government to domesticate these resolutions, women still suffer from gender gaps arising from gender inequality and unequal access to power, status and resources. In part, the challenges/setbacks to effective implementation of the domesticated resolutions, include; heightened physical risks to women due to insurgency in the North Eastern part of Nigeria, persistent relatively low budgetary allocation to gender equality programmes, social norms which limit women's access to power and productive resources, and significant reduction in the number of women appointed and elected into public offices (Archibong, Bassey & Nwagbara, 2018). For instance, women represent 47.5% and men represent 52.48% of registered voters in the 2023 General Elections. This percentage is not proportionate to the ratio of people in elective and appointive positions in Nigeria. The wide disparity in political office positions are consequences of gender-related hurdles and limitations that prevent the women from having equal opportunities with the men in the contest for either elective or appointive positions in the public space. Indeed, the Nigerian government has fallen short of implementing the 35 percent affirmative action that was adopted at the Beijing Declaration in 1995, as exemplified in the less than 5 percent of women occupants in the total elective positions in Nigeria.

It is evident that the gender-character of Nigeria's public space requires effective mainstreaming in order to align with the various global resolutions that the government has ratified. This call for immediate gender mainstreaming action reflects in the disproportionate, inequitable, unfair, and unjust composition of Nigeria's National Assembly.

Gender Composition of Nigeria's National Assembly

The history of Nigeria's National Assembly dates back to the country's independence on October 1st, 1960. The governing elites emulated the former colonialist's governance structure by the adoption of a bicameral legislature within the parliamentary system of government for its federal political arrangement. The House of Representatives and the Senate were composed of elected members that represented the electorates on the floor of the national parliament. This arrangement lasted for six years (till 1966), until the disruption by the military through the coup d'état of January 15th 1966 and the consequent coup d'état of 29th July, 1966. These events abruptly terminated Nigeria's democratic process, but the consequences were most telling on the legislative institutions.

The possibilities of hope for an enduring democratic system came with the conclusion of the transition to democracy programme in 1979. At this time, Nigeria adopted the US-styled

presidential system of government, whose major distinction with the parliamentary system is the separation of power, as opposed to the fusion of power. In other words, Nigeria created a system in which the parliament (National Assembly) was autonomous, yet, an arm of the government. As enshrined in the 1979 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, there is a federal bicameral legislature that is composed of representatives, directly elected by the people. This invention has become the permanent feature of Nigeria's democracy, despite the series of military interregnum that warranted fresh starts, as happened in 1992 and 1999. So, as designed in 1979, both the 1989 and 1999 constitutions of the Federal Republic of Nigeria dictates a bicameral legislature, composed of the Senate (Upper House of Assembly) and the House of Representatives (Lower House of Assembly).

The National Assembly derives its composition on the basis of constituent delineation, but it is also intentioned to be a representation of the broad spectrum of Nigerians as much as possible. Under this arrangement, the representation of the House of Assembly members is derived from raw population figures, and therefore not evenly distributed. It is based on the number of constituents per state, and a derivative of the number of constitutionally recognised Local Governments and Wards in each of the constituents.

From 1999 till date, Nigeria has had ten National Assemblies in accordance with the four-year tenure stipulated in the constitution for each assembly. For each of the assemblies, the House of Representatives is composed of three hundred and sixty members (360), while the Senate is composed of one hundred and nine members (109), and a senator representing the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The common feature of the two legislative chambers is the gender imbalance and inequality that remains a recurrent decimal in the composition of Nigeria's National Assembly.

The number of assembly positions on offer should evoke a higher level of female participation, in contrast to what currently subsists. It must however be noted that the government at various levels, and in conjunction with several non-governmental organisations have continued to strive to enhance women's participation and representation in electoral politics, particularly in the National Assembly. The country has ratified the "United Nations Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination against Women" (CEDAW) and established the National Commission for Women in 1989. In 2006, Nigeria developed a National Gender Policy, prescribing 35% affirmative action for women in appointive and elective positions. Other efforts include the Women Political Empowerment

Office, Nigeria Women Trust Fund, and the 100 Women Lobby Group. Despite all of these efforts, there is still a disappointing showing of Nigerian women within the political and policy environments. With reference to parliamentary representation, while the global percentage of women occupying parliamentary position is 42.4%, Nigeria ranks in the 181st position in the world ranking of women's parliamentary representation.

The table and charts below present the staggering illustration of men and women representation in Nigeria's National Assembly, over time.

Table 1: Gender Composition of Nigeria's National Assembly since 1979

Assembly Year	Senate					House of Representatives				
	Seats	Men	%	Women	%	Seats	Men	%	Women	%
1979	95	95	100	0	0	449	447	99.5	2	0.5
1992	91	90	98.9	1	1.1	593	580	97.8	13	2.2
1999	109	106	97.2	3	2.8	360	374	96.4	13	3.6
2003	109	105	96.3	4	3.67	360	339	94.2	21	5.8
2007	109	100	91.7	9	8.3	360	333	92.5	27	7.5
2011	109	102	93.5	7	6.5	360	335	93.1	25	6.9
2015	109	102	93.5	7	6.5	360	338	94	22	6
2019	109	102	93.5	7	6.5	360	350	97.2	10	2.7
2023	109	105	96.3	4	3.67	360	344	96.1	14	3.9

Source: National Bureau of Statistics and Global Data on National Parliament 2023.

Chart 1: Gender Composition of the Nigerian (1979-2023)

Chart 2: Gender Composition of the Nigerian House of Representatives (1979-2023)

The gender composition of Nigeria's National Assembly, which comprises the Senate and the House of Representatives, has historically been skewed heavily towards male representation. The first National Assembly in 1979 had a combination of 544 members (95 Senators and 449 House of Representatives members) with only two female members in the House of Representatives, constituting only 0.5% of the lower chamber and 0.3% of the whole national parliament. However, given the political consultations that preceded the return to democratic rule in 1992-1993, Lagos produced the first female Senator in the second National Assembly, while the House of Representatives has an increase from two (2) to thirteen (13) female members.

From the data presented above, even though with little margin of increase, the progression continues from 1999-2003 when the number of female Senators increased to three (3) and four (4) respectively. On the other hand, the House of Representatives grew in the number of female Representatives from 13 in 1999 to 21 in 2003, amounting to 5.8% growth. Conversely, the National Gender Policy, prescribing 35% affirmative action for women in appointive and elective positions had little effect on the number of female legislators after the 2007 General Elections. For the first time in the history of Nigeria's National Assembly, the number of female Senators rose to 9 accounting for 8.3% of the 109 Senators, while the number of female Representatives increased historically to 27 amounting to 7.5% of the 360 members.

However, in subsequent Assemblies from 2011 to 2019 the number of female senators has dwindled to seven (7), until 2023 when the number further depleted to four (4). This is the exact figure it was twenty years ago. In the lower chamber, however, the figure similarly depleted to twenty-five (25), twenty-two (22), and ten (10) between 2011 and 2019 respectively. In 2023, the figure slightly grew to its position of twenty-four years ago. Despite the efforts being made to address the gender disparities in representation at the National Assembly through the National Gender Policy, the overall trend reflects a predominantly male-dominated legislature.

The disparities in the gender composition of Nigeria's National Assembly underscore the persistent challenges in achieving gender equality and inclusive representation in the country's political landscape. Despite some progress over the years, women remain significantly underrepresented in positions of political power, particularly in the legislature. These disparities have far-reaching implications for democracy, good governance, and socio-economic development. A lack of gender diversity in the decision-making institutions limits the range of perspectives and experiences brought to the table, potentially hindering the development of policies and legislation that address the needs and concerns of all segments of society. Hence, it can be concluded that the Beijing Declaration of 1995, MDGs and SDGs are yet to be fully implemented in Nigeria.

Constraints on Gender Mainstreaming in Nigeria

Gender mainstreaming was created as a strategy for female inclusion in a male-dominated world. It seeks to find space for women in an otherwise suffocating environment controlled by men. It is a strategy for ensuring that gender perspectives are integrated into public policy and governance, through the various stages of formulation, implementation, monitoring and evaluation. The gender mainstreaming strategy is a means to an end rather than an end in itself, for it allocates legally binding number of positions for women, but cannot determine whether or not there will be qualified and competent women to occupy those positions. For instance, in situations where the constitution dictates a certain percentage of women representation (say 20%), and it so happens that the number of women available as representatives are fewer than the 20% representation, it therefore means that the women have short-changed themselves even when the positions are reserved for them. As mentioned earlier, there are quite a number of factors that are responsible for the seeming shortage of women to take up political positions.

The need for gender mainstreaming is of utmost importance to the national parliament because of the institution's law making responsibility. Besides this, the national parliament equally acts as checks on the possible excesses of the other arms of government- the Executive and the Judiciary. Thus, the process of achieving good governance is partly a responsibility of the national parliament- which must therefore be robustly representative in order to accommodate the interests of the generality of the people. A fair representation of women at such an august gathering will ensure maximum attention is focussed on matters that directly impact their livelihood and well-being.

In Nigeria, there are series of variables that undermine the successful implementation of gender mainstreaming policies. These variables include; traditional belief systems, norms, and prejudices; institutional barriers, and religious conventions, among others. The traditional African system profiles the woman as an embodiment of grace and sanctity, whose main preoccupation is to ensure decency in the home-front. The girl child is groomed to be the perfect wife and mother whose existence is tied to caring for the husband and the children. With these time-consuming and exhaustive responsibilities, the woman is railroaded into believing that her life revolves around nurturing and caring within the home-front. Even in the age of increasing opportunity of education for the female person, this constraint stands strong to prevent active participation in public life. As an uneducated and full-time housewife, the woman tends her children and her husband in a twenty-four hour full cycle, and through the years. Under such scenario, there is hardly any opportunity to seek for

participation or impact representation in politics. And in the event of opportunity for formal education, and eventual working life, the woman is still besieged with the demanding responsibility of taking care of the home-front such that the demands of active participation in the political process become an arduous, if not impossible task. The long hours of meetings, and particularly nocturnal meetings, and often times the violence and shenanigans involved in active participation in partisan politics make it impossible for the women to combine the expectations of their traditional roles with the demands of political participation.

The constraints to effective and adequate participation and representation of women in high politics can also be found in some institutionalised norms and practises of the political terrain. For instance, the financial resources required for membership of a political party is enormous for an average Nigerian woman, thus they are already shut out of the process since the political parties create the platform for participation and representation. Even when this huge hurdle is scaled, the aspirations of the women are also truncated at the level of seeking the party's nomination to stand for election. The financial requirement is humongous and beyond the reach of most women. And finally on occasions when some women overcome these hurdles, they are discouraged by the cost of campaigns, particularly because of the nature of the Nigerian environment in which aspirants for political offices are regarded as having "deep pockets" in which everyone deserves to benefit. These financial demands arguably pale into irrelevance when the high risk to personal safety is considered. It is indeed a truism that Nigeria's political process is driven by political violence and conflict, which overly exposes the female gender to physical harm and possible death. In effect, these institutionalised processes combine with peculiar environmental factors to prevent women from active participation in politics.

Related to the above constraints is the nature and character of the practise of religion in Nigeria. Majority of Nigerians align with the teachings and doctrines of the two Abrahamic religions (Islam and Christianity), and millions of them are adherents of the traditional African religions that are practised in accordance with the belief systems of each group. The underlining commonality among all these religious beliefs is the acceptance of the patriarchal system as the God-ordained system for societies. Meanwhile, inherent in the patriarchal system is the notion of subservience and obedience of the woman to the dictates of the man. Invariably, the man controls the home and the destiny of all within the home, and by extension, has the right to limit the aspirations and ambitions of the woman. This strong linkage between the Abrahamic and traditional religions, and patriarchy impedes the

participation and representation of women in Nigerian politics. According to Amusan, Saka, and Ahmed (2017, 8444):

In Nigeria, as elsewhere, religion and patriarchal values seem to be instruments of women domination and exclusion from politics. In cohort with others, they constitute factors constraining women's active political participation in politics. With patriarchal values and infusion of religion into politics, the Nigerian political setting displays an abashed preference for men dominance in politics and political leadership and aid the suppression of women's political ambitions and aspirations. It is within this context that the issue of affirmative action, gender equality and women empowerment are elevated to positions of importance in public discourse. However, promises of gender mainstreaming in Nigeria's politics to say the least, remains at the level of policy discourse.

In all of this, the religious institutions' adaptation of the patriarchal system that elevates man's societal responsibilities above the woman's by condemning the woman to the home-front is carried out through the sermons and teachings of the churches and mosques across Nigeria. To the religious leaders, women are not expected to be appointed or elected into positions of public responsibility, not so much because of the lack of intellectual capacity, but more about relegating their primary, traditional, and God-given responsibility to the background. Implicitly, when that happens, the society suffers since the collective outcomes of family upbringing determine the nature of the society. Religious organisations do not therefore encourage nor support the aspirations and ambitions of women for political positions. Through this arguable noble position, the religious groups have inadvertently prevented the women the opportunity of participation and representation in the public space.

Consequently, the aggregation of these constraints on women participation and representation makes it impossible to effectively implement gender mainstreaming policies that are made both nationally and internationally. This is so because the number of women available for either appointive or elective political positions are usually far below the 35% recommended threshold.

Conclusions

In summary, this research notes that there is a ginormous level of inequality between men and women in the processes of political participation and representation in Nigeria. Using Nigeria's National Assembly as case-study, the study highlights the disproportionate representation between men and women despite the government's ratification of several protocols and the enactment of several national legislations to evolve a system of gender mainstreaming that will generate equitable, just, and fair opportunities for participation and representation.

In the final analysis, the paper identifies three major constraints on the actualisation of gender mainstreaming models for women participation and representation in Nigeria. These constraints are; the nature of the traditional African systems of role designation, the institutional process of partisan politicking in Nigeria, and the role of religious organisations as actors in political socialisation and behaviour. The possibilities of an equitable gender mainstreaming model in line with universal protocols and national legislation can only be achieved if, and when the above constraints are tamed.

Recommendations

If the mere initiation of policies is enough to achieve results, Nigeria would not run afoul of the dictates of the Beijing Declaration, SDGs, and MDGs, and also the several national legislations. In effect therefore, recommendations for taming the constraints militating women participation can only be found in a deliberate, though semi-formal system of actions that aims specifically to dismantle the shackles of the disproportionate regime of political participation and representation. Some of the recommendations for achieving this objective are;

1. The traditional institutions should mobilise for a rejig of the systems of roles and responsibilities for women in alignment with extant reality. Specifically, the role of the girl-child and the woman should not be perceived as being limited to the home-front but should involve the opportunity for service to the society, and the whole of humanity. This is possible through support and encouragement for education, and also active participation in politics. This support should also include a reworked role-expectation system, such that societal roles are gender-blind to the extent that any man or woman should have the rights to aspire to achieve his or her ambitions without being bogged down by jaded role expectations.

2. The government should also regulate the political process, particularly, in the aspect of binding regulations in respect of financial requirements for political participation and representation. In effect, this must involve a determined drive to de-monetise politics such that level playing fields are created for all and sundry. To this end, there would no longer be enormous financial expectations that discourage the willingness to participate in politics.
3. While not denouncing the patriarchal system, the religious organisations must create a balance between the era of modernity and strict adherence to religious teachings. Women's rights should be treated as a significant part of human rights, towards the evolution of a system of equality in the society. Religious groups should not adorn the partisan toga, but occupy the vanguard of support and encouragement for women participation in politics.

Finally, it must be reiterated that the goals of gender mainstreaming can only be achieved when there are enough sufficient women that are in fact, available for elective and appointive political offices.

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